

1 **Modelling damage occurrence by snow and wind in forest ecosystems**

2
3

4 Olalla DÍAZ-YÁÑEZ^{1,*}, Blas MOLA-YUDEGO^{1,2}, José Ramón GONZÁLEZ-OLABARRIA³

5

6 ¹ School of Forest Sciences, University of Eastern Finland (UEF), PO Box 111, 80101
7 Joensuu, Finland.

8 ² Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO), P.O. Box, 115, 1431 Ås, Norway.

9 ³ Forest Sciences Centre of Catalonia (CTFC-CEMFOR), Ctra. de St. Llorenç de Morunys,
10 km 2, 25280 Solsona, Spain

11

12 *Corresponding author: Olalla Díaz-Yáñez. Address: School of Forest Sciences, University
13 of Eastern Finland, PO Box 111, 80101 Joensuu, Finland. Telephone: +358 40 8269912.

14 Email: olalla.diaz@uef.fi.

15

16

17

18 **Abstract**

19

20 Snow and wind damages are one of the major abiotic disturbances playing a major role in
21 forest ecosystems and affecting both stand dynamics and forest management decisions.
22 This study analyses the occurrence of wind and snow damage on Norwegian forests,
23 based on data from four consecutive forest inventories (1995-2014). The methodological
24 approach is based on boosted regression trees, a machine learning method aiming to
25 demonstrate the effects of different variables on damage probability and their interactions
26 as well as to spatialize damage occurrence to make predictions. In total, 313 models are
27 fitted to detect trends, interactions and effects among the variables. The main variables
28 associated with damage occurrence are consistent across all the models and include:
29 latitude, altitude and slope (related to site and location), and density, mean diameter and
30 mean height (related to forest characteristics). The results show that stand dominant
31 height is a key variable in explaining damage probability, whereas stand slenderness has
32 a limited effect. More heterogeneous forest structures make birch dominated stands more
33 resistant to damage. Finally, the models are translated into occurrence maps, to provide
34 landscape-level information on snow and wind damage hazard. Further application of the
35 models can be oriented towards assessing the probability of damage for alternate stand
36 management scenarios.

37

38 **Keywords:** Risk modelling, machine learning, boosted regression trees, forest
39 management

40

41 1. Introduction

42
43 Snow and wind damage in forests can result in large economic losses and changes in
44 stand dynamics, thus their consideration is vital if we want to improve the chances of
45 obtaining the specific management objectives (Gadow 2000). Such a consideration is even
46 more relevant under changing conditions, which can happen due to climatic variations or
47 shifts in the forest state. It is not precisely clear how climate is going to evolve in Northern
48 Europe (Feser et al. 2015; Mölter et al. 2016), but climatic changes leading to higher
49 frequency and intensity of the disturbances agents may increase snow and wind damage
50 in forests. Changes in the state of forests can occur, for example, by an increase in the
51 forest age and/or variations in the structure. If forests become more vulnerable, thereby
52 increasing their probability of experiencing snow and wind damage, we are to expect also
53 modifications in biodiversity (Lain et al. 2008; Thom and Seidl 2015), carbons stocks
54 (Schelhaas et al. 2003; Thom and Seidl 2015) or the provision of goods and services, such
55 as timber (Zubizarreta-Gerendiain et al. 2017). Thus, it is important to investigate why, and
56 which, forests are vulnerable to snow and wind damage, if we want to adopt management
57 actions that reduce the uncertainty in the expected outcomes.

58
59 Several studies, using different approaches and tools, have assessed the forest responses
60 to snow and wind damages through modelling (e.g. Seidl et al. 2011). Some of these
61 studies have focused on the effects following high-intensity storms that lead to
62 catastrophic damages events, and only include the affected areas (Dobbertin 2002;
63 Valinger and Fridman 2011; Hale et al. 2015). Approaches that only focus on catastrophic
64 events and affected areas obscure the reasons behind why certain stands are more
65 vulnerable than others, because such events have devastating effects on all stands,
66 regardless of the variations in the forest stability or the resistance traits of certain trees. In
67 this regard, instead of targeted post-event inventories, we required large, reliable and
68 comprehensive datasets covering larger temporal and spatial scales. Long-term
69 observations provide a better understanding of the overall forest susceptibility to damage,
70 and relate such damage to forests and site variables (Martín-Alcón et al. 2010; Albrecht et
71 al. 2010; Valinger and Fridman 2011), while large spatial scales capture the variability of
72 disturbance regimes and forest characteristics.

73
74 Models that aim to predict snow and wind damages in forests can be hybrid-mechanistic or
75 empirical. Hybrid-mechanistic models combine knowledge and processes information,
76 facilitating the analysis of potential different management scenarios. Examples of hybrid-
77 mechanistic models have been listed by Gardiner et al. (2008). Mechanistic models have
78 the advantage of being able to include tree failure in a physical manner, for example by
79 focusing on the critical wind speeds needed to uproot and break the stem of trees
80 (Gardiner et al. 2000, Schelhaas et al. 2007). On the other hand, and although with
81 exceptions (Nicoll et al. 2006), mechanistic models were developed based on a limited
82 number of observations, and only dealing with uniform stands of single species, leaving
83 opportunities to improve the representation of wind and snow damage processes on more
84 heterogeneous stands. Empirical models can account for all of the ecological complexity
85 reflected in the collected dataset, and help to identify the key factors involved. Studies
86 using empirical approaches often diverge in the relative importance of the variables, due to
87 the obvious variations in climate, location and forest conditions among studies from
88 different areas (Mitchell 2013). Predictors used in these empirical studies have included:
89 variables concerning the topographic situation (Mitchell et al. 2001; Albrecht et al. 2012;
90 Pasztor et al. 2014; Hanewinkel et al. 2014); variables referring to the soil and site
91 conditions (Mitchell et al. 2001); and variables describing stand- and tree-level
92 characteristics such as mean basal area (Albrecht et al. 2010; Valinger and Fridman 2011;

93 Pasztor et al. 2014), density (Pukkala et al. 2016), tree size (height, diameter and
94 slenderness) (Martín-Alcón et al. 2010; Albrecht et al. 2010; Pukkala et al. 2016), stand
95 structure (Hanewinkel et al. 2014; Pukkala et al. 2016), dominant species and species
96 diversity (Albrecht et al. 2010; Valinger and Fridman 2011; Albrecht et al. 2012; Pasztor et
97 al. 2014).

98
99 One of the disadvantages of the traditional empirical modelling, such as logistic models
100 (Fridman and Valinger 1998; Jalkanen and Mattila 2000) is the difficulty in understanding
101 the complex damage process from the resulting model. Identifying how variables are
102 involved in, and affect, forest vulnerability to snow and wind is complex. There are many
103 correlations among the variables involved, making it difficult to interpret the influence of
104 certain of these without considering the correlated variables. New methods based, on
105 machine learning, such as boosted regression trees, can consider a large range of
106 variables and, at the same time, fit complex non-linear relationships, accommodate
107 missing values, handle variable interactions and still deliver good predictive models (Elith
108 et al. 2008). Although machine-learning models are difficult to interpret, they can be
109 summarised in a way that provides powerful insights, and represent a valuable tool for use
110 in making informed decisions. Several studies have proved that machine-learning
111 approaches are powerful tools for identifying characteristics related to damage
112 phenomena, and providing a clear understanding of the meaningful variables (Kamimura
113 et al. 2008; Albrecht et al. 2012).

114
115 In this study we focused on the probability of the occurrence of snow and wind damage in
116 forest stands. The analysis relies on empirical data, collected from several consecutive
117 National Forest Inventories from Norway, including 20 years' worth of data. Based on an
118 adequate methodological framework that addresses the complexity of the data structure,
119 the specific objectives of this contribution are to (i) assess which variables are relevant to
120 explain the damage occurrence, evaluating their relationships and interactions (ii) identify
121 areas susceptible to damage spatializing the probability of occurrence.

122
123

124 **2. Material and Methods**

125

126 **2.1. Data sources**

127

128 The data used was from the Norwegian National Forest Inventory (NFI), collected during
129 the period 1995–2014, corresponding with to the 7th, 8th, 9th and 10th inventories. The
130 Norwegian NFI is a systematic inventory of permanent circular plots of 250 m² in a 3 x 3
131 km grid representing the entire distribution and diversity of Norwegian forest types. For
132 plots divided by a stand border (e.g., a plot is part forest, part water, or encompasses two
133 forest types with very different productivity parameters), only the most forested part of the
134 plot was considered. Plots were also divided into four different forest types, based on their
135 dominant species and according to their basal area presence: spruce (spruce > 70%); pine
136 (pine > 70%); birch (birch > 70%); and mixed forests (when no single species accounted
137 for more than 70% of the basal area). Most of the observations were categorized as mixed
138 forests and birch forest types, 62 and 10% respectively; conifer dominated plots
139 represented the 12 and 16% for pine and spruce, respectively.

140

141 The occurrence of forest damage was identified and measured from an area of 1000 m²
142 around the centre of each permanent plot; we considered those plots where such damage
143 was recorded in that area to be damaged plots. Following the inventory protocols
144 (Skoglandskap 2007), stand damage occurrence was recorded when: it was believed to

145 have taken place during the five years prior to measurement; it had an effect on the future
 146 economic development of the stand; and it compromised regeneration, or decreased
 147 volume production and wood quality. We considered snow and wind damage together, as
 148 climatic conditions in Nordic areas make the combination of both agents the cause of
 149 damage (Valinger and Fridman 1999).

150
 151 The 7th NFI (1995–1999) was used as a reference inventory to provide information
 152 concerning initial stand characteristics, and the estimated variables that described the
 153 forest stand and site were used as predictors (Table 1). The predicted variable was
 154 presence/absence of snow and wind damage, and this was defined and evaluated for
 155 those plots included in the 8th–10th inventories (2000–2014); damage presence was
 156 assigned to those plots that were recorded, at least once, as damaged, whereas damage
 157 absence was assigned to plots with no damage recorded in the three inventories (15
 158 years). In total, 7097 plots were considered for modelling purposes, of which 6486 plots
 159 were not classed as damaged.

160
 161 **Table 1** Stand level explanatory variables used in the models

	Variable name (units)	Description
Site	Altitude (m)	Meters above sea level.
	Relief (categorical)	Shape or roughness of the surface in the plot location divided in 7 categories according to the inventory protocols (Skoglandskap 2007).
	Latitude (m)	North-south position of the plot.
	Slope (%)	Slope measured in percentage.
	Soil type (categorical)	Type of soil: mineral or organic.
Forest	Species (categorical)	It defines the stand forest type and corresponds with the dominant species of the plot: spruce, pine, birch or mixed.
	Mean diameter (cm)	Basal area weighted mean diameter using all the trees in each plot.
	Dominant height (m)	Dominant height, calculated following the inventory protocols (Skoglandskap 2007).
	Slenderness (m/cm)	Ratio between mean calculated height (m) of all the trees in the plot and mean diameter (cm) before the damage.
	Density (trees ha ⁻¹)	Number of trees per hectare.
	Gini index	Structure index, calculated by basal area of the trees. Higher values indicate more structural heterogeneity; lower values indicate more homogeneous stands.
		$Gini\ coefficient = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N g_i - g_j }{2n^2 \bar{g}} \quad [0, 1]$
		where N is the number of trees in the plot, i, j two different trees in the plot, g_i the basal area of the tree i , g_j the basal area of the tree j and \bar{g} the mean basal area of the plot.
	Shannon coefficient	Species diversity index, calculated by the basal area, for Spruce, Birch, Pine, other conifer and other broadleaves, before

the damage. Higher values indicate more diverse plots, lower values indicate less diverse plots.

$$\text{Shannon index} = \sum_{i=1}^S p_i \ln p_i [0, \ln S]$$

where p_i is the basal area probability: g_i/G , being g_i the basal area of the i specie and G the total basal area of the plot. i , is the number of species ranging from $1 \dots S$

162

163

164

165 2.2. Statistical methods

166

167 The statistical analysis was based on boosted regression trees (BRT). This approach
168 combines machine learning and statistical techniques, and consists of adding regression
169 trees fitted in a forward stepwise process (Friedman et al. 2000; Elith et al. 2008). The
170 stepwise process starts with the creation of a single tree that minimises the loss function;
171 then a new tree is fitted, using the residuals of the first one. By these means, the first
172 developed model is updated to incorporate the information from the new tree. The
173 residuals of the latest updated model are recursively used to fit a new tree, and so forth.
174 The existing trees do not change, as only the fitted values of each observation are re-
175 estimated each time a new tree is added. The final model reflects the contributions of all of
176 the developed trees, providing more stable and accurate values than would a single tree.

177

178 The BRT model calibration is defined by four parameters – the learning rate (or shrinkage
179 parameter), the bag fraction, the tree complexity, and the number of trees required for
180 optimal prediction. The learning rate determines the contribution of each new tree to the
181 growing model, and it is always substantially lower than 1, higher values being related to
182 faster learning. The bag fraction provides information on which fraction of the entire data
183 should be drawn randomly to fit the new tree. This parameter includes a random
184 probabilistic component, making each run model different, and is aimed at improving
185 model accuracy, speed of model creation, and the reduction of overfitting (Friedman
186 2002). Tree complexity controls the number of fitted interactions among variables, and
187 determines the number of splits in each tree; for example, a value of 1 will present only
188 one split, meaning that the model does not consider interactions; a value of 2 will result in
189 two splits, and two interactions. The optimal number of trees is selected based on the
190 three previous parameters. The values fitted by the final model are computed as the sum
191 of all of the predictions of the trees, multiplied by their respective learning rates.

192

193 We built different models, based on alternative values for learning rate (0.005, 0.001, 0.01,
194 0.05, 0.1), bag fraction (0.2, 0.5, 0.8) and tree complexity (every unit between 1 and 10),
195 and 10-fold cross-validation was performed to estimate the optimal number of trees in
196 each case, following Elith et al. (2008). The models were fitted assuming a Bernoulli
197 distribution, since the response variable was the presence/absence of snow and wind
198 damage, and were designed for each of the forest types and for all of the forest types
199 combined, resulting in a total of 750 models (5 forest types + combined, 5 levels of
200 learning rate, 3 bag fractions and 10 levels of tree complexity). The statistical analyses
201 were developed in R version 3.3.2 (R Core Team 2013), and the BRT models were based
202 on the 'dismo' extension of the 'gbm' package (Elith 2017).

203

204 The deviance value of the models was used to select the model with the best predictive
205 performance for each forest type. Additionally, the performance and behaviour of all
206 developed models was analysed. For each model, the cross-validation deviance was

207 calculated, and analysed as a function of the different model parameters (tree complexity,
208 bag fraction and learning rate). The relative importance of the predictor variables was
209 calculated by considering the number of times each variable was used for splitting,
210 weighted by improvement to the model as a result of the split, and averaged across all of
211 the trees in the models, following Elith et al. (2008). Model behaviour was evaluated
212 through partial dependence plots, showing the effect of each of the variables on the
213 response by accounting for the average effects of all other predictors in the model. In order
214 to identify the fitted interaction effects, we tested the partial dependencies between the
215 response and predictor variables. The model predictions were obtained for each pair of
216 predictor variables, setting all other predictors to their means. We plotted the most
217 significant pairwise interactions – those variables with higher relative significance. Finally,
218 the models with the best predictive performance were used to create a predictive map of
219 the estimated probability of damage occurrence. The map was created by using
220 observations from the period 2010–14, divided by forest type, as the data input. The
221 predicted values were presented in the map as a spatially-weighted average, calculated
222 through Gaussian kernel smoothing.
223
224

225 **3. Results**

226

227 Some models could not be computed for the parameters considered due to the lack of
228 sufficient data. In total, 92 models were developed for all of the forest types combined, 63
229 models were developed for spruce-dominated stands, 68 for birch stands and 90 for mixed
230 stands; due to the reduced number of damaged plots, pine only produced one model,
231 which was not included in the study. We found that, as we increased the BRT parameters,
232 we obtained better performance levels, thereby increasing the randomness in the models,
233 the learning rate and the tree complexity (Figure 1). Variation in the BRT parameter values
234 also changed the number of trees that were fitted per model; increasing learning rate and
235 tree complexity decreased the number of trees. Variation of the BRT parameter values
236 also provided different model performance values. Relatively few models were fitted with
237 the fastest feasible learning rates, and none with the highest learning rate considered
238 (0.1). In all of the developed models, reducing tree complexity decreased model deviance,
239 although such variation was limited. In models predicting damage occurrence for all
240 species together, increasing bag fraction reduced model deviance. For all of the models,
241 increasing learning rate and tree complexity reduced the number of optimal trees required
242 for minimum error.
243

244

245 **Fig. 1** Models deviance as a function of the tree complexity (number of interactions), bag
 246 fraction (stochasticity) and learning rate (shrinkage). The coloured dots correspond with
 247 the selected model in each forest type with minimum deviance resulting from the best
 248 combination of bag, tree complexity and learning rate values

249

250 Variable importance of the best predictive models (Figure 2), and across all models, were
 251 consistent. Among the site-related variables, latitude, altitude and slope were the most
 252 significant. Density, diameter and height were the three most significant variables related
 253 to forest characteristics, although the significance of diameter varied for each forest type.
 254 On the other hand, the dominating species had a low contribution to the models predicting
 255 damage occurrence for all species together.
 256

Fig. 2 Variable importance of the best predictive models represented as the contribution of each variable to the final model as a percentage scaled so that the sum adds to 100.

The marginal effect of each of the variables was consistent across all models (Figures 3 and 4). Steeper slopes made all forest types more susceptible to being affected by wind and snow. Similarly, northernmost forests at higher elevations had a higher probability of damage occurrence, particularly on mixed forests, or when the data was analysed for all forest types without previous segregation. How forest characteristics affected the probability of damage occurrence varied depending on the dominant species. Increasing stand dominant height above 20 m caused a sharp increase in the probability of damage occurrence on spruce and mixed stands. Increasing mean diameter in the initial stages of development for stands with small mean diameters reduced the probability of damage on mixed stands, while relatively small increments, for diameters below 40 cm, increased the probability of damage occurrence in birch- and spruce-dominated stands. Increasing density up to a 2000 tree ha⁻¹ threshold increased the damage occurrence probability in all of the forest types. Increasing slenderness did not influence the damage occurrence probability on any of the forest types. Increasing stand heterogeneity, once a threshold level of 0.5 was reached on the Gini coefficient, had a negative impact on the damage occurrence probability, except for in birch stands, where highly heterogeneous stands appeared to be less susceptible to being affected by snow and wind. Finally, species diversity, as explained by the Shannon index, did not have an effect, except for high values in mixed stands, where highly diverse stands were more prone to suffer damage episodes.

282

283

284

285

286

287

288

Fig. 3 Marginal dependency plots for the three site variables with highest variable importance and their comparative effect among the three forest types (Spruce, Birch and Mixed) and all of them together (All). The solid lines represent the selected models and the coloured areas the variability around the selected models from all the developed models. Y axes are centred to have zero mean over the data distribution

289
290

291 **Fig. 4** Marginal dependency plots of the six forest variables with highest variable
292 importance across all the models and their comparative effect among the three forest
293 types (Spruce, Birch and Mixed) and all the forest types together (All). The solid lines
294 represent the selected models and the coloured areas the variability around the selected
295 models from all the developed models. Y axes are centred to have zero mean over the
296 data distribution

297

298 The nature and magnitude of the fitted interactions varied across the selected models
299 (Figure 5). The model for all species together had the highest interaction levels between
300 altitude and latitude, stand dominant height and latitude, and density and altitude. In the
301 selected model for spruce-dominated stands, the most important pairwise interactions of
302 continuous variables were between density and stand dominant height, Gini coefficient
303 and altitude, but their interaction values were much lower compared to the model for all
304 species together. In the selected model for birch-dominated stands, the strongest
305 interaction was between the Gini coefficient and stand mean diameter. In the selected
306 model for mixed stands, the most important pairwise variables, due to their strongest

307 interactions, were between latitude and altitude, Shannon index and latitude, slenderness
 308 and altitude, and dominant height and diameter. In the selected model for mixed stands,
 309 the interaction between latitude and altitude had the same pattern as the one presented
 310 for all species together, and therefore was not plotted again in Figure 5.
 311

312
 313 **Fig. 5** Variable interactions on the selected models. The plots are three-dimensional
 314 dependence plots for the strongest interactions in the models among continuous variables,
 315 all are plotted against the range of fitted values (z axis)
 316

317 The most important interactions of the models presented different effects. In the model
 318 predicting damage occurrence for all species together, the highest fitted values occurred
 319 when the stands were at high altitude regardless of latitude values, when the stands were
 320 at high altitude regardless of stand density, and when the stands had dominant heights
 321 above 20 m for all latitude values. In the model predicting damage occurrence for spruce-
 322 dominated stands, the highest fitted values occurred when the dominant height was above

323 25 m for all density values. On birch-dominated stands, the highest damage probability
 324 values occurred when the stand was older and even-aged – high stand mean diameter
 325 and homogeneous structure (low Gini coefficient values). In the model predicting damage
 326 occurrence for mixed stands, the highest fitted values occurred when the stand was less
 327 diverse (lower Shannon index values) at high latitudes, at high altitude regardless of the
 328 slenderness, and when the mean stand diameter was low, and the dominant height was
 329 high.

330
 331 Finally, using the best predictive models for each forest type, a spatial prediction was
 332 developed in order to identify vulnerable areas (Figure 6). According to the model
 333 predictions using the most up-to-date plot data available, the most vulnerable areas for
 334 spruce- and birch-dominated were in the south-west of the country, although birch-
 335 dominated vulnerable areas extended across the whole country. Mixed stands were most
 336 vulnerable in the north of the country.
 337

338
 339 **Fig. 6** Spatial predictions at country level and in selected regions using each of the
 340 developed models. Country level and the selected region have the same scale in each
 341 forest type except for spruce. Map border lines adapted from (Kartverket 2014), original
 342 licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

343
 344
 345 **4. Discussion**

346
 347 Among the different disturbances resulting in forest damage, snow and wind play an
 348 significant role in Norway (Díaz-Yáñez et al. 2016). Analysis of damage occurrence,
 349 however, presents serious challenges. On one hand it requires a long period of time to
 350 effectively reveal patterns and trends, and on the other hand, the potential exploratory
 351 variables are complex, often interact with each other, and do not necessarily present a
 352 linear relationship with the probability of damage occurrence. The present study addressed
 353 this first challenge by covering an interval of 20 years, which resulted in accessible

354 information on damage occurrence of 15 years from the measurements, making it possible
355 to compare the characteristics of damage and undamaged stands, and to use that
356 information to identify which variables and values make a stand more vulnerable to
357 experiencing damage. The second challenge, related to the complexity of potential
358 exploratory variables, was addressed by using a BRT-based approach. BRT is a machine-
359 learning method that provides an accurate description of variable relationships and
360 interactions, having the advantage of being flexible, providing useful insights into complex
361 ecological datasets, making it possible to identify complex interactions among variables,
362 and facilitating interpretation of model behaviour with a high level of accuracy.
363

364 Unfortunately, one of the limitations of this approach relates to the applicability of the
365 models to other areas or conditions; whereas maps and predictions resulting from BRT
366 models have a good level of accuracy, the original models are not easily transferable, as is
367 the case for regression models, for example, where the estimates of the parameters would
368 suffice for replication in other conditions or locations. Another limitation concerns the risk
369 of overfitting. Although BRT models may allow overfitting, this is appropriately addressed
370 by using different mechanisms (e.g., introducing stochasticity into the fitting process); also,
371 it has been proved that overfitting does not compromise the predictions, even providing
372 better performance than other methods, such as logistic models (Elith et al. 2006, 2008;
373 Leathwick et al. 2006). Arguably, the higher predictive power, as well as the capacity to
374 reveal complex interactions, compensates for the overfitting limitation, as reflected in its
375 increasing popularity. Particularly in forest sciences, the use of BRT has increased in
376 recent years. It has been used to investigate storm resistance between species (Albrecht
377 et al. 2012), to map site indices of different species (Aertsens et al. 2010), to estimate yield
378 biomass (Van Meerbeek et al. 2014; Mola-Yudego et al. 2016) and forest productivity
379 (Verkerk et al. 2015), to account for the geographical variation in soil organic carbon
380 stocks (Nanko et al. 2017), and to estimate species or disease distribution and richness,
381 related to ecological variables (Elith et al. 2006, 2008; Leathwick et al. 2006; Randall and
382 van Woesik 2015), among others. In this study, we assessed the effects of different values
383 for the different model parameters, and analysed their effects on the predictive
384 performance of the models. As discussed in previous studies (Leathwick et al. 2006), this
385 is a necessary step for each dataset, as preselecting the values of the model parameters
386 could lead to models with higher predictive errors.
387

388 Although the response variable was measured on a bigger area than the plot and, in
389 consequence, may relate to other trees than those described in the plot, the plot-level
390 information is a valid representation of the stand, and therefore highly correlated to the
391 damage measurement. The portfolio of variables considered in predicting the damage
392 occurrence was in agreement with previous studies (Albrecht et al. 2012; Mitchell 2013;
393 Pasztor et al. 2014; Hanewinkel et al. 2014; Pukkala et al. 2016), and the results showed
394 that their role across all the developed models was consistent. Concerning variables
395 related to location, latitude and altitude had a contribution in our models, as the spatial
396 distribution of the stand plays an important role in how exposed it is to damaging agents;
397 typically, stands located at higher altitudes and more northerly latitudes are more exposed
398 to snow and wind. Previous studies have also considered topographic information, by
399 using a variable proxy for topographic exposure (Scott and Mitchell 2005), whilst in this
400 study we used directly measured variables instead, as we want to understand their
401 behaviour individually. Our results showed, however, that the combined effects of altitude
402 and latitude did not necessarily increase the probability of damage occurrence, and did not
403 equally affect all species. This can be explained by the growing conditions of the trees
404 located in northern latitudes that make them more adapted to extreme conditions (Nicoll et
405 al. 2008), and even more resistant than stands in more sheltered areas. Although other

406 studies have found negative correlations between altitude and damage (Lanquaye-Opoku
407 and Mitchell 2005; Albrecht et al. 2012), they have also concluded that there are many
408 other factors that might be relevant when considering topographic information; for
409 example, local conditions such as stand borders, which are very relevant in relation to
410 wind damage, and the effects of local climatic conditions, as in this study, with many
411 coastal areas and high elevations. From our results, there was also a clear positive
412 correlation between slope and damage occurrence, which contradicts previous wind
413 studies (Hanewinkel et al. 2004; Lanquaye-Opoku and Mitchell 2005).

414
415 Concerning variables related to the forest conditions, the results underlined the importance
416 of tree's height, this being consistently the most significant variable in all of the models,
417 which is acknowledged as being a primary variable for estimating stand vulnerability to
418 wind damage (Schmidt et al. 2010). Diameter was the second most significant variable,
419 also indicating that increasing diameter increases vulnerability, which contradicts many
420 previous studies, but agrees with Canham et al. (2001) and Pukkala et al. (2016), probably
421 indicating that the average stand height was also increasing due to the high correlation
422 between diameter and height (Pukkala et al. 2016).

423
424 In addition to height and diameter, independently, previous studies have also discussed
425 the importance of their ratio in relation to damage vulnerability (Fridman and Valinger
426 1998; Peltola et al. 1999a). Our results agree with the general idea that increasing trees
427 slenderness, or height, results in higher stand vulnerability; however, the results showed
428 that height explained a more substantial part of the probability of damage occurrence,
429 whereas slenderness had a very limited effect. The fact that slenderness provides
430 information on tree-level stability and not stand level could explain its lack of influence in
431 our models. There are recommendations that suggest that only looking at slenderness
432 should be avoided, as it could lead to a false conclusion (Albrecht et al. 2010); for
433 example, lower ratios have been found to represent more stability against snow breakage
434 damage (Peltola et al. 1999b), but lower values could also represent trees with larger
435 crowns that easily store snow, thus making them more vulnerable (Weiskittel et al. 2009).
436 Our study's conclusions are in the same direction, indicating that mean stand slenderness
437 by itself is not a good predictor for determining stand-level resistance to snow and wind
438 damage occurrence, although it has proven to be a relevant variable in determining
439 damage intensity and type in spruce and mixed stands (Díaz-Yáñez et al. 2017).

440
441 Although the individual form of the trees in a stand is highly relevant in determining their
442 vulnerability, it can be greatly influenced by stand density. Previous studies have
443 highlighted that denser stands, with taller trees, are less stable, while low-density stands
444 result in the development of more resistant trees (Petty and Worrell 1981; Mitchell et al.
445 2001; Pukkala et al. 2016). On the other hand, other studies have not found a relationship
446 between density and a decrease in stand vulnerability (Hanewinkel et al. 2014). Our
447 results showed that dominant height and mean diameter were highly correlated with stand
448 density in spruce-dominated stands, indicating that denser stands, with higher dominant
449 heights and larger mean diameters, had higher probabilities of damage occurrence.

450
451 It is assumed that stand structure has an influence on stand stability, making more
452 heterogeneous structures more resistant to damage from snow and wind (Griess and
453 Knoke 2011; Pukkala et al. 2016). In this study, the effects of stand structure were
454 analysed through the Gini index (Valbuena et al. 2012), which indicated that more
455 heterogeneous stand structures reduced the probability of damage occurrence in birch-
456 dominated stands, but not in spruce or mixed stands, or when considering all species
457 together. It has been also discussed that irregular structures tend to have individual trees

458 with lower slenderness, making the trees less vulnerable (Kenk and Guehne 2001; Mason
459 2002). Although silvicultural treatments oriented towards more irregular stands can result
460 in more stable stands, it would be problematic to change from an even- to uneven-aged
461 structure in a stand, as that would leave individual dominant trees that were not adapted to
462 increased wind loading exposed (Mason 2002; Martín-Alcón et al. 2010). It is also relevant
463 to consider the site-specific biomechanical adaptation of trees to agent exposure, as
464 acclimatising trees to a certain level of exposure will fail if the exposure levels are
465 exceeded (Coutts 1995; Bonnesoeur 2016). Therefore, silvicultural treatments aimed at
466 modifying stand structure, such as thinning (Pukkala et al. 2016), should be applied with
467 caution, and other related parameters, such as tree anchoring through soil depth and the
468 thigmomorphogenetical acclimation of trees, should be considered. Moreover, silvicultural
469 treatments that change forest structures should aim for slow transformation, making
470 changes in the early stages, when stand heights are low.

471
472 In the models for all species combined, the variable defining the species had a mean
473 contribution below 5%, indicating that location and stand-specific variables had a greater
474 impact on damage probability than the dominant species, which agrees with previous
475 studies, in which variable species composition was not significant (e.g., Hanewinkel et al.
476 2014). Nevertheless, there were differences between a stand's dominant species and the
477 behaviour of certain other variables, such as diameter or height. It is important to note that
478 species-specific characteristics, such as rooting or crown shape, were not included as
479 specific variables in our models, and were assumed to be implicitly represented by the
480 variable that differentiated plot species dominance (Albrecht et al. 2010) as a necessary
481 simplification due to lack of more detailed records. This induces us to consider that the
482 seemingly lack of importance of this variable does not mean that there are not differences,
483 but rather that the species-based differences related to tree's architecture should be more
484 specifically considered, whenever available data make it possible.

485
486 Finally, there are at least four potential applications for the models developed in this study:
487 1) the production of landscape-level hazard maps for snow and wind damage; 2)
488 identification of the key factors controlling damage occurrence; 3) evaluation of risk for
489 individual stands; and 4) the simulation of stand vulnerability to damage occurrence under
490 variable conditions. Combined with the probability of stand damage proportion (Díaz-
491 Yáñez et al. 2017), these can be used to estimate optimal silvicultural treatments. Despite
492 the limitations of the available data, and the method considered, we regard the present
493 models as a promising approach to analyse dynamic interaction of disturbances by snow
494 and wind and forest structure, as affected by management interventions or natural
495 changes.

496 497 **Acknowledgements**

498
499 We are grateful to the forest doctoral school of the University of Eastern Finland for their
500 kind economic support, as well as to the SIS-REDCLIM, funded by the Norwegian Institute
501 of Bioeconomy Research. Dr. González-Olabarria also thanks the Ramón y Cajal Program
502 from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Education and the CERCA Programme of the
503 Generalitat de Catalunya for supporting his work. We also want to thank Prof. Timo
504 Pukkala for his valuable comments and Robert John Wiedenfeld for the English
505 corrections on an earlier version of this manuscript.
506

507 508 **Conflict of interest**

509 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

510

References

- Aertsen W, Kint V, Orshoven JV, et al (2010) Comparison and ranking of different modelling techniques for prediction of site index in Mediterranean mountain forests. *Ecol Model* 221:1119–1130. doi: 10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2010.01.007
- Albrecht A, Hanewinkel M, Bauhus J, Kohnle U (2010) How does silviculture affect storm damage in forests of south-western Germany? Results from empirical modeling based on long-term observations. *Eur J Forest Res* 131:229–247. doi: 10.1007/s10342-010-0432-x
- Albrecht A, Kohnle U, Hanewinkel M, Bauhus J (2012) Storm damage of Douglas-fir unexpectedly high compared to Norway spruce. *Ann For Sci* 70:195–207. doi: 10.1007/s13595-012-0244-x
- Bonnesoeur V, Constant T, Moulia B, Fournier M (2016) Forest trees filter chronic wind-signals to acclimate to high winds. *New Phytol* 210:850–860. doi: 10.1111/nph.13836
- Canham CD, Papaik MJ, Latty EF (2001) Interspecific variation in susceptibility to windthrow as a function of tree size and storm severity for northern temperate tree species. *Can J For Res* 31:1–10. doi: 10.1139/cjfr-31-1-1
- Coutts MP, Grace J (1995) Wind and trees.
- Díaz-Yáñez O, Mola-Yudego B, Eriksen R, González-Olabarria JR (2016) Assessment of the Main Natural Disturbances on Norwegian Forest Based on 20 Years of National Inventory. *PLoS ONE* 11:e0161361–16. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0161361
- Díaz-Yáñez O, Mola-Yudego B, González-Olabarria JR, Pukkala T (2017) How does forest composition and structure affect the stability against wind and snow? *For Ecol Manage* 401:215–222. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2017.06.054
- Dobbertin M (2002) Influence of stand structure and site factors on wind damage comparing the storms Vivian and Lothar. *For Snow Landsc Res* 77:187–205.
- Elith J (2017) dismo: Species distribution modeling. R package version 1.1-4. 1–68.
- Elith J, Graham CH, Anderson RP, et al (2006) Novel methods improve prediction of species' distributions from occurrence data. *Ecography* 29:129–151. doi: 10.1111/j.2006.0906-7590.04596.x
- Elith J, Leathwick JR, Hastie T (2008) A working guide to boosted regression trees. *J Anim Ecology* 77:802–813. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2656.2008.01390.x
- Feser F, Barcikowska M, Krueger O, et al (2015) Storminess over the North Atlantic and northwestern Europe-A review. *QJR Meteorol Soc* 141:350–382. doi: 10.1002/qj.2364
- Fridman J, Valinger E (1998) Modelling probability of snow and wind damage using tree, stand, and site characteristics from *Pinus sylvestris* sample plots. *Scand J For Res* 13:348–356. doi: 10.1080/02827589809382994
- Friedman J (2002) Stochastic gradient boosting. *Computational Statistics and Data Analysis* 38:367–378.

- Friedman J, Hastie T, Tibhirani R (2000) Additive logistic regression: a statistical view of boosting (with discussion and a rejoinder by the authors). *Ann Stat* 28:337–407.
- Gadow Von K (2000) Evaluating risk in forest planning models. *Silva Fenn* 34:181–191.
- Gardiner, B., Peltola, H., & Kellomäki, S. (2000). Comparison of two models for predicting the critical wind speeds required to damage coniferous trees. *Ecological Modelling*, 129:1–23. [http://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3800\(00\)00220-9](http://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3800(00)00220-9)
- Gardiner, B., Byrne, K., Hale, S., Kamimura, K., Mitchell, S. J., Peltola, H., & Ruel, J.-C. (2008) A review of mechanistic modelling of wind damage risk to forests. *Forestry* 81:447–463. doi: 10.1093/forestry/cpn022
- Griess VC, Knoke T (2011) Growth performance, windthrow, and insects: meta-analyses of parameters influencing performance of mixed-species stands in boreal and northern temperate biomes. *Can J For Res* 41:1141–1159. doi: 10.1139/x11-042
- Hale SE, Gardiner B, Peace A, et al (2015) Comparison and validation of three versions of a forest wind risk model. *Environmental Modelling and Software* 68:27–41. doi: 10.1016/j.envsoft.2015.01.016
- Hanewinkel M, Kuhn T, Bugmann H, et al (2014) Vulnerability of uneven-aged forests to storm damage. *Forestry* 87:525–534. doi: 10.1093/forestry/cpu008
- Hanewinkel M, Zhou W, Schill C (2004) A neural network approach to identify forest stands susceptible to wind damage. *For Ecol Manage* 196:227–243. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2004.02.056>
- Jalkanen A, Mattila U (2000) Logistic regression models for wind and snow damage in northern Finland based on the National Forest Inventory data. *For Ecol Manage* 135:315–330. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127\(00\)00289-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127(00)00289-9)
- Kamimura K, Gardiner B, Kato A, et al (2008) Developing a decision support approach to reduce wind damage risk - a case study on sugi (*Cryptomeria japonica* (L.f.) D.Don) forests in Japan. *Forestry* 81:429–445. doi: 10.1093/forestry/cpn029
- Kartverket (2014) N250 Map data.
- Kenk G, Guehne S (2001) Management of transformation in central Europe. *For Ecol Manage* 151:107–119. doi: 10.1016/S0378-1127(00)00701-5
- Lain EJ, Haney A, Burris JM, Burton J (2008) Response of vegetation and birds to severe wind disturbance and salvage logging in a southern boreal forest. *For Ecol Manage* 256:863–871. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2008.05.018
- Lanquaye-Opoku N, Mitchell SJ (2005) Portability of stand-level empirical windthrow risk models. *For Ecol Manage* 216:134–148. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2005.05.032
- Leathwick JR, Elith J, Francis MP, et al (2006) Variation in demersal fish species richness in the oceans surrounding New Zealand: an analysis using boosted regression trees. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 321:267–281. doi: 10.3354/meps321267

- Martín-Alcón S, González-Olabarria JR, Coll L (2010) Wind and snow damage in the Pyrenees pine forests: effect of stand attributes and location. *Silva Fenn* 44:399–410. doi: <https://doi.org/10.14214/sf.138>
- Mason WL (2002) Are irregular stands more windfirm? *Forestry* 75:347–355. doi: [10.1093/forestry/75.4.347](https://doi.org/10.1093/forestry/75.4.347)
- Mitchell SJ (2013) Wind as a natural disturbance agent in forests: a synthesis. *Forestry* 86:147–157. doi: [10.1093/forestry/cps058](https://doi.org/10.1093/forestry/cps058)
- Mitchell SJ, Hailemariam T, Kulis Y (2001) Empirical modeling of cutblock edge windthrow risk on Vancouver Island, Canada, using stand level information. *For Ecol Manage* 154:117–130. doi: [10.1016/S0378-1127\(00\)00620-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127(00)00620-4)
- Mola-Yudego B, Rahlf J, Astrup R, Dimitriou I (2016) Spatial yield estimates of fast-growing willow plantations for energy based on climatic variables in Northern Europe. *Glob Change Biol Bioenergy*. doi: [10.1111/gcbb.12332](https://doi.org/10.1111/gcbb.12332)
- Mölter T, Schindler D, Albrecht A, Kohnle U (2016) Review on the Projections of Future Storminess over the North Atlantic European Region. *Atmosphere* 7:1–40. doi: [10.3390/atmos7040060](https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos7040060)
- Nanko K, Hashimoto S, Miura S, et al (2017) Assessment of soil group, site and climatic effects on soil organic carbon stocks of topsoil in Japanese forests. *Eur J Soil Sci* 68:547–558. doi: [10.1111/ejss.12444](https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12444)
- Nicoll BC, Gardiner B, Peace AJ (2008) Improvements in anchorage provided by the acclimation of forest trees to wind stress. *Forestry* 81:389–398. doi: [10.1093/forestry/cpn021](https://doi.org/10.1093/forestry/cpn021)
- Nicoll BC, Gardiner B, Rayner B, Peace AJ (2006) Anchorage of coniferous trees in relation to species, soil type, and rooting depth. *Can J For Res* 36:1871–1883. doi: [10.1139/x06-072](https://doi.org/10.1139/x06-072)
- Pasztor F, Matulla C, Zuvella-Aloise M, et al (2014) Developing predictive models of wind damage in Austrian forests. *Ann For Sci* 72:289–301. doi: [10.1007/s13595-014-0386-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13595-014-0386-0)
- Peltola H, Kellomäki S, Väisänen H (1999a) Model computations of the impact of climatic change on the windthrow risk of trees. *Climatic Change* 41:17–36. doi: [10.1023/A:1005399822319](https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1005399822319)
- Peltola H, Kellomäki S, Väisänen H, Ikonen VP (1999b) A mechanistic model for assessing the risk of wind and snow damage to single trees and stands of Scots pine, Norway spruce, and birch. *Can J For Res* 29:647–661. doi: [10.1139/x99-029](https://doi.org/10.1139/x99-029)
- Petty JA, Worrell R (1981) Stability of coniferous tree stems in relation to damage by snow. *Forestry* 54:115–128. doi: [10.1093/forestry/54.2.115](https://doi.org/10.1093/forestry/54.2.115)
- Pukkala T, Laiho O, Lähde E (2016) Continuous cover management reduces wind damage. *For Ecol Manage* 372:120–127. doi: [10.1016/j.foreco.2016.04.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2016.04.014)
- R core Team (2013) R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. URL <http://www.R-project.org/>.

- Randall CJ, van Woesik R (2015) Contemporary white-band disease in Caribbean corals driven by climate change. *Nature Climate change* 5:375–379. doi: 10.1038/nclimate2530
- Seidl, R., Fernandes, P. M., Fonseca, T. F., Gillet, F., Jönsson, A. M., Merganičová, K., et al. (2011). Modelling natural disturbances in forest ecosystems: a review. *Ecological Modelling*, 222: 903–924. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2010.09.040>
- Schelhaas M-J, Nabuurs GJ, Schuck A (2003) Natural disturbances in the European forests in the 19th and 20th centuries. *Glob Chang Biol* 9:1620–1633. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-2486.2003.00684.x
- Schelhaas, M.-J., Kramer, K., Peltola, H., van der Werf, D. C., & Wijdeven, S. M. J. (2007). Introducing tree interactions in wind damage simulation. *Ecological Modelling*, 207: 197–209. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2007.04.025>
- Schmidt M, Hanewinkel M, Kändler G, et al (2010) An inventory-based approach for modeling single-tree storm damage — experiences with the winter storm of 1999 in southwestern Germany. *Can J For Res* 40:1636–1652. doi: 10.1139/X10-099
- Scott RE, Mitchell SJ (2005) Empirical modelling of windthrow risk in partially harvested stands using tree, neighbourhood, and stand attributes. *For Ecol Manage* 218:193–209. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2005.07.012
- Skoglandskap (2007) Handbook of Forestry and Landscape 06/2007 National Forest Inventory, field instructions 2007. Håndbok fra Skog og landskap 06/2007 Landsskogtakseringens feltinstruks 2007. 1–117.
- Thom D, Seidl R (2015) Natural disturbance impacts on ecosystem services and biodiversity in temperate and boreal forests. *Biol Rev* 91:760–781. doi: 10.1111/brv.12193
- Valbuena R, Packalen P, Martín-Fernández S, Maltamo M (2012) Diversity and equitability ordering profiles applied to study forest structure. *For Ecol Manage* 276:185–195. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2012.03.036
- Valinger E, Fridman J (2011) Factors affecting the probability of windthrow at stand level as a result of Gudrun winter storm in southern Sweden. *For Ecol Manage* 262:398–403. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2011.04.004
- Valinger E, Fridman J (1999) Models to assess the risk of snow and wind damage in pine, spruce, and birch forests in Sweden. *Environ Manage* 24:209–217. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s002679900227>
- Van Meerbeek K, Van Beek J, Bellings L, et al (2014) Quantification and Prediction of Biomass Yield of Temperate Low-Input High-Diversity Ecosystems. *Bioenerg Res* 7:1120–1130. doi: 10.1007/s12155-014-9444-6
- Verkerk PJ, Levers C, Kuemmerle T, et al (2015) Mapping wood production in European forests. *For Ecol Manage* 357:228–238. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2015.08.007
- Weiskittel A, Kenefic L, Seymour R, Phillips L (2009) Long-term effects of precommercial thinning on the stem dimensions, form and branch characteristics of red spruce and balsam fir crop trees in Maine, USA. *Silva Fenn* 43:1–13. doi: 10.14214/sf.196

Zubizarreta-Gerendiain A, Pukkala T, Peltola H (2017) Effects of wind damage on the optimal management of boreal forests under current and changing climatic conditions. *Can J For Res* 47:246–256. doi: 10.1139/cjfr-2016-0226

